

Influence of Planting Distance and Insecticide Spray Application on Performance of Cowpea [*Vigna Unguiculata* (L.) Walp] in Forest-Transition Zone of Ghana

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ABSTRACT

The study was conducted to determine varietal response of cowpea [(i) Zamzam and (ii) Soronko] to planting distance [(i) 50 x 20 cm (ii) 60 x 20 cm] and insecticide spray application [(i) 2 sprays (ii) 3 sprays (iii) no spray (control)] in forest-transition zone of Ghana. Two field experiments were conducted for two years at College of Agriculture Education, University of Education, Winneba, Asante Mampong campus during 2016 and 2017 cropping seasons.

The 2 x 2 x 3 factorial experiment was laid in a randomized complete block design with three replications. The result showed that there was a significant ($p < 0.05$) difference between Zamzam and Soronko in number filled pods per plot, number of pods per plant, number of pest infested seeds per plot, percentage plant establishment, number of plants harvested and number of pods per plant during 2016 and 2017 cropping seasons respectively. Zamzam planted 50 x 20 cm spacing had the highest shoot and fresh root weight at 63 days after planting during the 2017 cropping season. Zamzam planted at 50 x 20 cm or 60 x 20 cm spacing and sprayed 3 times had the highest percentage plant establishment, a number of unfilled pods per plot and number of plants harvested respectively. Soronko planted 60 x 20 cm spacing with 2 times spraying had the highest number of filled pods per plot. In conclusion for high vegetative growth of cowpea to be used as fodder, farmers are to grow Zamzam and plant using 50 x 20 cm spacing and spray 2 times. Farmers are encouraged to grow Soronko using 50 x 20 cm or 60 x 20 cm spacing and spray 2 times for a high number of pods per plant, number of filled pods per plot and least number of pest infested seeds per plot.

Keywords: Soronko, Zamzam, insecticide spray application, planting distance, cowpea

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The cowpea crop (*Vigna unguiculata* (L.) Walp.) is the most important grain legume in many parts of the world (Takim and Uddin, 2010). The crop is mostly grown as an intercrop with maize and preferred by farmers due to the role it plays in maintaining soil fertility through nitrogen-fixation (Asiwe *et al.*, 2009a), it can improve soil structure with its deep roots, it reduces erosion and weeds through its rapid growth and soil coverage (Ola *et al.*, 2015), and its nutritive value as fodder for livestock (Dzemo *et al.*, 2010). The cowpea grain is highly nutritious and contains about 15.06- 38.5% protein although this differs among cowpea varieties (Ravelombola *et al.*, 2016). In Ghana, the fresh leaves and pods and dry seeds are consumed in various dietary combinations. The dry grains are boiled and eaten with 'gari' and fried ripened plantain. The flour obtained from the dry cowpea seeds can also be made into dough and fried in cooking oil called 'kose' (Danso, 2016). Currently, cowpea is regarded as a food security crop in Ghana (MoFA, 2010). In spite of the numerous benefits from cowpea and its yield potential in the savanna regions of Ghana, the major constraints to cowpea production are insect pests and diseases (ICRISAT, 2013) and variations in climatic conditions. Insect pests pose a serious threat to cowpea production and attack the crop from germination to storage. Again yields of

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cowpea remain low, mainly due to the frequent use of unimproved varieties as well as poor cultural practices. Cultural practices which are usually utilized in cowpea pest management include planting distance. Efforts have been made to improve cowpea production in Ghana through various means, including the introduction of new varieties (Addo-Quaye *et al.*, 2011) and more productive agricultural technologies. None of these improved varieties could achieve the best performance without recommendations of appropriate and specific planting distance and spraying regimes. High cowpea yields can be achieved if the crop is protected from insect pests. Insect control choices include chemical, biological and cultural controls. However, most small scale farmers do not adequately control insect pests due to the high cost of chemicals and labour. Insecticide application should be integrated with other cultural practices such as variety and planting distance for insect pest management in cowpea. The study, therefore, investigates into effects of variety, planting distance and insecticide spray application on cowpea (*Vigna unguiculata* L. Walp) growth, yield and yield components in the forest-transition zone of Ghana.

2.0. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Description of Study Area

Two field experiments were carried out for two years at College of Agriculture Education of the University of Education, Winneba, Asante Mampong campus during 2016 and 2017 cropping season. The experimental site is gently inclined and is well drained. The climatic conditions during the field research periods show that differences in environmental factors (rainfall, temperature, and relative humidity) were shown during both 2016 and 2017 cropping seasons. The overall monthly rainfall during the 2016 cropping season was 382.2 mm, and it happened between May and July 2016 with the highest occurring in May and June. The average monthly temperature of the experimental site during the 2016 cropping season ranged between 20.9 °C to 31.6 °C with the highest daily of 31.6 °C occurring in May 2016. The average monthly relative humidity ranged from 62 to 96 % with the highest occurring between June and July. In the 2017 cropping season, the overall monthly rainfall was 417.6 mm, and it occurred from May to July 2017 with the peak in May and June. The average monthly temperature of the experimental site for the 2017 cropping season was between 21.7 °C to 32.4 °C, with the highest daily of 32.4 °C occurring in May. The mean monthly relative humidity ranged from 63% to 97% with the highest occurring between June and July.

The soil at the experimental site has been categorized by FAO/UNESCO (Food and Agricultural Organization/United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization) [FAO/UNESCO, 1988] legend as Chronic Luvisol and locally as the Bediesi series with a pH range of 4.0-6.5 and is suitable for root, cereal, vegetable and legume crops production (Asiamah, 1988).

2.2 Experimental Design and Planting

In each location, the experimental site was laid out in a 2 x 2 x 3 factorial experiment in a randomized complete block design (RCBD) with three replications consisting of two cowpea varieties, two planting distance and three spraying regime which was assigned to each block. The two cowpea varieties (Zamzam and Soronko) obtained from CSIR- Crop research Institute in Fumesua near Kumasi, Ghana were grown under 2 plant distance [(i) 50 x 20 cm (ii) 60 x 20 cm] and 3 spraying regime [(i) 2 spray (ii) 3 spray (iii) no spray (control)]. Cowpea plants were sprayed at 35 and 45 days after planting with Karate and at 55 days after planting with Cymethoate at the rate of 600 ml/ ha. The total field size of 38.8 .0 m x 16.0 m (620.8 m²) was weeded followed by ploughing and harrowing due to the absence of stumps. Individual treatment plot measured 2.0 m and 2.4 m wide to respective treatments with each row 4.0 m long and 1.0 m left between plots and 2.0 m between blocks. Three seeds of Zamzam and Soronko were planted 0.5 m and 0.6 m respectively between rows and 0.2 m between plants at a depth of 2-4 cm and later thinned to 2 plants per hill. Each treatment plot had 4 rows of 40 plant per row and 160 plants per plot.

2.3 Data Collection and Analysis

Data were collected on seventy two plants from the two central rows, and the means were taken. The quantitative traits measured were percentage plant establishment, number of plants harvested, shoot and root fresh and dry weights, number of pods per plant, number of unfilled filled pods per plot and number of pest infested seeds per plot. The percentage plant establishment was measured at 4 weeks after planting by counting the number of plants that established from the two central rows and the percentage plant establishment subsequently estimated. A number of plants harvested were counted from the two central rows from the day of planting until the day of harvest. Shoot and root fresh and dry weights were determined on six randomly selected plants from the border rows at 4 weeks after planting and at two weeks interval. Plants were destructively sampled and separated into shoot and root and weighed using an electronic weighing scale. After destructive sampling for fresh shoot and root weights gain, samples were oven dried at 70 °C until the constant temperature was attained. Dried samples were then weighed using an electronic weighing scale. A number of pods per plant, number of unfilled and filled pods per plot and number of pest infested seeds per plot was counted from the two harvestable areas. Data were subjected to ANOVA using GenStat Statistical Package, version 11.1. A least significant difference (LSD) was used to separate means at 5% level of probability.

3.0 RESULTS

3.1 Vegetative growth

3.1.1 *Shoot fresh weight*

There was a significant difference between Soronko and Zamzam in fresh shoot weight at 21 and 35 days after planting (DAP) during the 2016 cropping season (Table 1). The fresh shoot weights increased with Zamzam from 49 to 63 DAP than Soronko during the 2016 cropping season. There was a significant difference between Zamzam and Soronko in fresh shoot weight from 21 DAP to 49 DAP during 2017 cropping season (Table 1). There was no significant difference between the two varieties in fresh shoot weight at 63 DAP during 2017 cropping season (Table 1). There was an increasing trend in fresh shoot weight in both cowpea varieties for the entire 2016 and 2017 cropping seasons (Table 1). There was a significant difference between 50 x 20 cm from 60 x 20 cm planting distance in fresh shoot weight at 21 and 35 DAP during the 2016 and 2017 cropping seasons respectively. However, there was no significant difference between 50 x 20 cm from 60 x 20 cm planting distance in fresh shoot weight from 35 to 63 DAP and at 21, 49 and 63 DAP during 2016 and 2017 cropping seasons respectively (Table 1). There was a significant difference between Soronko grown on 50 x 20 cm from Zamzam grown on 50 x20 cm and 60 x 20 cm spacing as well as soronko has grown on 60 x 20 cm spacing in fresh shoot weight at 21 DAP during the 2016 cropping season (Table 1). Soronko grown on 50 x 20 cm differed significantly from Zamzam grown on 50 x 20 cm in fresh shoot weight at 35 DAP during the 2016 cropping season (Table1). There was no significant difference between variety x planting distance in fresh shoot weight from 49 to 63 DAP during the 2016 cropping season and from 21 to 63 DAP during the 2017 cropping season. There was no significant difference between spraying regime and variety x spraying regime interaction in fresh shoot weight for the entire growing season in both 2016 and 2017 cropping seasons (Table.1).

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Table 1: Shoot fresh weight as influenced by plant spacing and spraying regime from 21 to 63 days after planting for 2016 and 2017 cropping seasons

SHOOT FRESH WEIGHT / DAYS AFTER PLANTING									
TREATMENT	YEAR	2016	2017	2016	2017	2016	2017	2016	2017
Variety		21		35		49		63	
Zamzam		165.3	80.1	570.0	591.0	736.0	1471.0	877.0	1421.0
Soronko		204.8	46.4	683.	276.0	689.0	717.0	735.0	1216.0
LSD (P = 0.05)		20.5	12.16	104.2	107.4	NS	284.9	NS	NS
Planting Distance									
50 × 20cm		196.0	66.3	629.0	492.0	713.0	1116.0	816.0	1342.0
60 × 20cm		174.1	60.3	624.0	374.0	712.0	1072.0	796.0	1295.0
LSD (P = 0.05)		20.5	NS	NS	107.4	NS	NS	NS	NS
Spraying Regime									
2 sprays		179.1	65.4	613.0	480.0	788.0	1191.0	846.0	1142.0
3 sprays		182.2	63.6	586.0	373.0	662.0	880.0	754.0	1234.0
No sprays		193.8	60.8	682.0	447.0	688.0	1203.0	819.0	1579.0
LSD (P = 0.05)		NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS
Var. x Planting Distance									
Zm × 50 × 20cm		162.7	81.6	536.0	642.0	739.0	1467.0	917.0	1521.0
Zm × 60 × 20cm		167.9	78.7	605.0	539.0	733.0	1475.0	837.0	1320.0
SK × 50 × 20cm		229.3	51.0	723.0	343.0	686.0	765.0	715.0	1164.0
SK × 60 × 20cm		180.2	41.9	644.0	210.0	692.2	669.0	755.0	1269.0
LSD (P = 0.05)		29.0	NS	147.2	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS
Var. x Spraying Regime									
Zm × 2 sprays		158.0	86.5	553.0	665.0	896.0	1538.0	1011.0	1191.0
Zm × 3 sprays		152.7	83.9	526.0	518.0	632.0	1187.0	701.0	1409.0
Zm × no sprays		185.2	70.0	633.0	589.0	681.0	1688.0	919.0	1663.0
SK × 2 sprays		200.2	44.3	673.0	295.0	680.0	843.0	681.0	1094.0
SK × 3 sprays		211.7	43.3	647.0	299.0	692.0	589.0	806.0	1060.0
SK × no sprays		202.5	51.7	730.0	304.0	695.0	719.0	718.0	1496.0
LSD (P = 0.05)		NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS

Zm= Zamzam

SK= Soronko

NS= non - significant

Var. = Variety

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Table 2: Root fresh weight as influenced by plant spacing and spraying regime from 21 to 63 days after planting for 2016 and 2017 cropping seasons

ROOT FRESH WEIGHT / DAYS AFTER PLANTING										
TREATMENT	YEAR	2016	2017	2016	2017	2016	2017	2016	2017	
Variety		21		35		49		63		
Zamzam		8.8	8.9	25.4	26.2	32.6	53.8	28.7	62.1	
Soronko		1.6	5.9	29.9	15.7	39.3	32.8	37.1	43.7	
LSD (P = 0.05)		1.25	1.60	3.71	4.01	4.35	7.43	5.04	11.30	
Planting Distance										
50 × 20cm		10.1	7.6	27.2	23.8	35.9	43.5	33.7	53.7	
60 × 20cm		9.3	7.2	28.1	18.2	35.9	43.1	32.1	52.1	
LSD (P = 0.05)		NS	NS	NS	4.01	NS	NS	NS	NS	
Spraying Regime										
2 sprays		9.2	7.0	26.2	22.0	37.8	46.9	31.8	43.5	
3 sprays		10.1	7.8	26.6	19.3	32.6	37.9	31.3	54.4	
No sprays		9.8	7.5	30.1	21.7	37.3	45.1	35.5	60.9	
LSD (P = 0.05)		NS								
Var. x Planting Distance										
Zm × 50 × 20cm		9.1	9.1	24.7	28.5	34.6	53.4	30.4	67.2	
Zm × 60 × 20cm		8.5	8.7	26.1	23.9	30.6	54.2	26.9	57.0	
SK × 50 × 20cm		11.1	6.2	29.7	19.1	37.3	33.6	36.9	40.2	
SK × 60 × 20cm		10.2	5.6	30.1	12.4	41.2	32.0	37.2	47.2	
LSD (P = 0.05)		NS								
Var. x Spraying Regime										
Zm × 2 sprays		8.5	8.0	25.1	28.1	36.7	54.2	29.2	49.3	
Zm × 3 sprays		8.6	9.8	23.3	24.1	28.8	49.9	25.2	65.9	
Zm × no sprays		9.3	9.0	27.8	26.5	32.2	57.5	31.7	71.2	
SK × 2 sprays		10.0	6.0	27.3	15.8	39.0	39.7	34.5	37.7	
SK × 3 sprays		11.6	5.8	30.0	14.5	36.3	26.0	37.3	42.8	
SK × no sprays		10.3	6.0	32.5	17.0	42.5	32.7	39.3	50.7	
LSD (P = 0.05)		NS								

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Table 3: Shoot dry weight as influenced by plant spacing and spraying regime from 21 to 63 days after planting for 2016 and 2017 cropping seasons

SHOOT DRY WEIGHT / DAYS AFTER PLANTING										
TREATMENT	YEAR	2016	2017	2016	2017	2016	2017	2016	2017	
Variety		21		35		49		63		
Zamzam		16.2	9.5	24.1	18.4	33.5	24.0	32.7	26.3	
Soronko		17.8	6.7	26.6	19.6	28.3	24.6	32.0	31.3	
LSD (P = 0.05)		NS	1.62	NS	NS	1.39	NS	NS	2.73	
Planting Distance										
50 × 20cm		17.6	8.0	24.9	19.8	29.6	23.6	31.3	28.4	
60 × 20cm		16.5	8.3	25.7	18.2	32.3	25.0	33.5	29.2	
LSD (P = 0.05)		NS	NS	NS	NS	1.39	NS	NS	NS	
Spraying Regime										
2 sprays		16.7	8.5	27.3	20.3	30.6	25.6	33.2	30.3	
3 sprays		16.1	8.3	25.5	18.2	30.3	23.5	33.5	26.8	
No sprays		18.2	7.5	23.1	18.5	31.9	23.8	30.5	29.3	
LSD (P = 0.05)		NS								
Var. x Planting Distance										
Zm × 50 × 20cm		16.2	9.4	22.3	18.2	31.8	23.7	32.1	26.3	
Zm × 60 × 20cm		16.3	9.7	25.8	18.7	35.2	24.4	33.4	26.3	
SK × 50 × 20cm		19.0	6.5	27.4	21.5	27.3	23.4	30.5	30.5	
SK × 60 × 20cm		16.6	6.8	25.7	17.6	29.4	25.7	33.5	32.1	
LSD (P = 0.05)		NS								
Var. x Spraying Regime										
Zm × 2 sprays		15.6	10.1	26.3	18.3	32.6	25.0	31.6	27.3	
Zm × 3 sprays		14.6	10.0	24.0	18.6	32.8	23.9	35.0	24.4	
Zm × no sprays		18.5	8.5	21.8	18.5	35.1	23.3	31.6	27.3	
SK × 2 sprays		17.8	7.0	28.3	22.3	28.6	26.3	34.8	33.3	
SK × 3 sprays		17.6	6.6	27.0	17.8	27.8	23.1	32.0	29.3	
SK × no sprays		18.0	6.5	24.3	18.6	28.6	24.3	29.3	31.3	
LSD (P = 0.05)		NS								

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Table 4: Root dry weight as influenced by plant spacing and spraying regime for 2016 and 2017 cropping seasons.

ROOT DRY WEIGHT/DAYS AFTER PLANTING

TREATMENT	YEAR	2016	2017	2016	2017	2016	2017	2016	2017
Variety		21		35		49		63	
Zamzam		2.7	2.6	5.4	4.8	8.9	13.6	6.1	13.5
Soronko		3.0	1.9	5.7	2.5	9.9	9.2	7.5	10.5
LSD (P = 0.05)		NS	0.58	NS	1.05	NS	2.10	1.08	2.80
Planting Distance									
50 × 20cm		2.9	2.4	5.5	4.4	9.1	11.4	6.8	12.3
60 × 20cm		2.8	2.1	5.6	2.8	9.7	11.4	6.7	11.6
LSD (P = 0.05)		NS	NS	NS	1.05	NS	NS	NS	NS
Spraying Regime									
2 sprays		2.9	2.3	5.3	3.8	9.5	12.4	6.4	9.5
3 sprays		2.9	2.4	5.4	3.0	8.4	10.2	6.3	12.6
No sprays		2.8	2.0	6.0	4.1	10.82	11.6	7.6	13.8
LSD (P = 0.05)		NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS
Var. x Planting Distance									
Zm × 50 × 20cm		2.7	2.7	5.1	5.5	8.7	13.6	6.4	15.0
Zm × 60 × 20cm		2.6	2.4	5.7	4.1	9.1	13.7	5.7	12.0
SK × 50 × 20cm		3.1	2.1	5.8	3.3	9.4	9.2	7.3	9.6
SK × 60 × 20cm		3.0	1.7	5.5	1.6	10.4	9.2	7.6	11.3
LSD (P = 0.05)		NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS
Var. x Spraying Regime									
Zm × 2 sprays		2.5	2.6	5.3	5.1	9.6	13.1	5.5	10.5
Zm × 3 sprays		2.6	2.8	5.1	4.1	7.5	13.3	6.8	14.6
Zm × no sprays		3.0	2.2	5.8	5.1	9.6	14.5	6.8	15.3
SK × 2 sprays		3.3	2.0	5.3	2.5	9.3	11.6	7.1	8.5
SK × 3 sprays		3.1	2.1	5.6	1.8	9.3	7.1	8.5	10.6
SK × no sprays		2.6	1.6	6.1	3.1	11.1	8.8		12.3
LSD (P = 0.05)		0.63	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS

3.1.2 Root fresh weight

There was a significant difference between Soronko and Zamzam in fresh root weight from 35 to 63 days after planting (DAP) during the 2016 cropping season (Table 2). There was, however, a significant difference between Zamzam and Soronko in fresh root weight from 21 to 63 days after planting (DAP) during the 2017 cropping season (Table. 2). There was an increasing trend in fresh root weight in both varieties for the entire 2016 and 2017 cropping seasons (Table 2). There was no significant difference between 50 x 20 cm from 60 x 20 cm planting distance in fresh root weight from 21 to 63 DAP during 2016 and 2017 cropping seasons except at 35 DAP in which 50 x 20 cm differed significantly from 60 x 20 cm during the 2017 cropping season. There was no significant difference between the three spraying regimes in fresh root weight from 21 to 63 DAP during 2016 and 2017 cropping seasons (Table 2). There was no significant difference between variety x planting distance and variety x spraying regime interaction in fresh root weight for the entire growing 2016 and 2017 cropping seasons (Table 2).

3.1.4 Shoot dry weight

There was no significant difference between Soronko and Zamzam in dry shoot weight from 21 to 63 days after planting (DAP) during the 2016 cropping season except at 49 DAP in which Zamzam differed significantly from Soronko at the same growing period (Table 3). There was a significant difference between Zamzam and Soronko in dry shoot weight at 21 DAP during the 2017 cropping season (Table 3). There was a significant difference between Soronko and Zamzam in dry shoot weight at 63 DAP during the 2017 cropping season (Table 3). There was no significant difference between 50 x 20 cm from 60 x 20 cm planting distance in dry shoot weight from 21 to 63 DAP during 2016 and 2017 cropping seasons except at 49 DAP in which 60 x 20 cm differed significantly from 50 x 20 cm during the 2016 cropping season (Table 3). There was no significant difference between the three spraying regimes in dry shoot weight from 21 to 63 DAP during 2016 and 2017 cropping seasons (Table 3). There was no significant difference between variety x planting distance and variety x spraying regime interaction in shoot dry weight for the entire 2016 and 2017 cropping seasons (Table 3).

3.1.5 Root dry weight

There was no significant difference between Soronko and Zamzam in root dry weight from 21 to 49 DAP during the 2016 cropping season except at 63 DAP in which Soronko differed significantly from Zamzam (Table 4). There was a significant difference between Zamzam and Soronko in root dry weight for the entire 2017 cropping season (Table 4). There was no significant difference between 50 x 20 cm from 60 x 20 cm planting distance in root dry weight from 21 to 63 DAP during 2016 and 2017 cropping seasons except at 35 DAP in which 50 x 20 cm differed significantly from 60 x 20 cm during the 2017 cropping season (Table 4). There was no significant difference between the three spraying regimes, variety x planting distance and variety x spraying regime interaction in root dry weight for the entire 2016 and 2017 cropping seasons (Table 4). There was a significant difference between Soronko sprayed two times from Zamzam sprayed 2 or 3 times as well as Soronko without insecticide spray (Table 4).

3.1.5 Percentage plant establishment

The percentage plant establishment for 2016 and 2017 cropping season for the two cowpea varieties (Zamzam and Soronko) ranged from (70.2- 98.8) and (97.2-80.8) respectively (Table 5). There was no significant difference between Zamzam and Soronko in percentage plant establishment during the 2016 cropping season (Table 5). However, Zamzam differed significantly from Soronko in percentage plant establishment during the 2017 cropping season (Table 5). There was no significant difference between 50 x 20 cm from 60 x 20 cm planting distance, Spraying regime, variety x planting distance interaction and variety x spraying regime in

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percentage plant establishment in both 2016 and 2017 cropping seasons (Table.5). The two cowpea varieties grown during the 2017 cropping season and with similar treatment produced higher percentage plant establishment than those produced during the 2016 cropping season (Table 5).

3.1.6 Number of plants harvested

There was no significant difference between the two cowpea varieties, planting distance, spraying regime, variety × planting distance and variety × spraying regime interaction in a number of plants harvested during the 2016 cropping season (Table 5). There was a significant difference between Zamzam and Soronko in a number of plants harvested during the 2017 cropping season (Table 5). Zamzam without insecticide spray differed significantly from Soronko sprayed two or three times in a number of plants harvested during the 2017 cropping season. There was no significant difference between Zamzam sprayed 2 and 3 times or without insecticide spray as well as Soronko without insecticide spray in a number of plants harvested during the 2017 cropping season (Table 5). There was no significant difference between planting distance, spraying regime and variety × planting distance interaction in a number of plants harvested during the 2017 cropping season (Table 5). The two cowpea varieties grown during the 2016 cropping season and with similar treatment produced a higher number of plants harvested than those produced during the 2017 cropping season (Table 5).

Table 5: Percentage plant establishment and number of plants harvested as influenced by plant spacing and spraying regime for 2016 and 2017 cropping seasons

TREATMENT Variety	YEAR	PERCENTAGE PLANT ESTABLISHMENT		NUMBER OF PLANTS HARVESTED	
		2016	2017	2016	2017
Zamzam		70.2	98.8	58.0	44.0
Soronko		70.2	80.8	57.0	32.0
LSD (P = 0.05)		NS	6.41	NS	5.04
Planting Distance					
50 × 20cm		70.0	90.1	57.0	37.0
50 × 20cm		70.4	89.4	59.0	39.0
LSD (P = 0.05)		NS	NS	NS	NS
Spraying Regime					
2 sprays		70.1	89.7	57.0	38.0
3 sprays		71.0	88.3	60.0	33.0
No sprays		69.5	91.3	57.0	43.0
LSD (P = 0.05)		NS	NS	NS	NS
Var. x Planting Distance					
ZM + 50 × 20cm		70.2	98.8	59.0	42.0
ZM + 60 × 20cm		70.2	98.9	58.0	45.0
SK + 50 × 20cm		69.7	81.5	55.0	32.0
SK + 60 × 20cm		70.6	80.1	60.0	32.0
LSD (P = 0.05)		NS	NS	NS	NS
Var. x Spraying Regime					
ZM + 2 sprays		70.3	98.4	57.0	43.0
ZM + 3 sprays		71.0	99.1	62.0	44.0
ZM + no sprays		69.3	98.8	57.0	46.0
SK + 2 sprays		70.0	81.0	56.0	33.0
SK + 3 sprays		71.0	77.5	59.0	23.0
SK + no sprays		69.6	83.8	57.0	41.0
LSD (P = 0.05)		NS	NS	NS	8.73

3.1.7. Number of unfilled pods per plot

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There was no significant difference between the two cowpea varieties, planting distance, spraying regime, variety \times planting distance and variety \times spraying regime interaction in number of unfilled pods per plot during the 2016 and 2017 cropping seasons except during the 2017 cropping season in which Soronko without spraying differed significantly from Soronko sprayed two or three times as well as Zamzam sprayed 2 or 3 times (Table 6). Soronko and Zamzam grew on 50 x 20 cm and 60 x 20 cm spacing and sprayed 2, 3 or without insecticide spray and their interactions produced a higher number of unfilled pods per plot during the 2016 cropping season than during the 2017 cropping season (Table 6).

3.1.8 Number of filled pods per plot

There was a significant difference between Zamzam and Soronko in a number of filled pods per plot during the 2016 cropping season (Table 6). However, Soronko differed significantly from Zamzam in a number of filled pods per plot during the 2017 cropping season (Table 6). There was no significant difference between planting distance, spraying regime, variety \times planting distance and variety \times spraying regime interaction in a number of filled pods per plot in both 2016 and 2017 cropping seasons (Table 6).

3.1.9 Number of pods per plant

There was a significant difference between Zamzam and Soronko in a number of pods per plant during the 2016 cropping season (Table 7). Soronko differed significantly from Zamzam in a number of pods per plant during the 2017 cropping season (Table 7). There was no significant difference between planting distance, spraying regime, variety \times planting distance and variety \times spraying regime interaction in a number of pods per plant in both 2016 and 2017 cropping seasons (Table 7). Soronko and Zamzam have grown on 50 x 20 cm and 60 x 20 cm spacing and sprayed 2, 3 or without insecticide spray and their interactions produced a higher number of pods per plant during the 2017 cropping season than during the 2016 cropping season (Table 7).

3.1.10 Number of pest infested seeds per plot

There was a significant difference between Zamzam and Soronko in a number of pest infested seeds per plot during the 2016 cropping season (Table 7). There was no significant difference between the two cowpea varieties in a number of pest infested seeds per plot during the 2017 cropping season (Table 7). There was no significant difference between planting distance, spraying regime, variety \times planting distance and variety \times spraying regime interaction in a number of pest infested seeds per plot in both 2016 and 2017 cropping seasons (Table 7). Zamzam has grown on 50 x 20 cm and 60 x 20 cm and sprayed 2 or 3, and its interactions produced a higher number of pest infested seeds per plot during the 2016 cropping season than during the 2017 cropping season (Table 7).

Table 6: Number of filled pods per plant and number of unfilled pods per plot as influenced by plant spacing and spraying regime for 2016 and 2017 cropping seasons

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Treatment Variety	Number of Filled Pods Per Plot		Number of Unfilled Pods Per Plot		
	Year	2016	2017	2016	2017
Zamzam		512.0	361.0	33.0	9.0
Soronko		306.0	526.0	28.0	13.0
LSD (P=0.05)		91.9	89.1	NS	NS
Plant distance					
50 x 20 cm		415.0	432.0	32.0	11.0
60 x 20 cm		403.0	456.0	29.0	11.0
LSD (P=0.05)		NS	NS	NS	NS
Spraying Regime					
2 sprays		380.0	468.0	34.0	8.0
3 sprays		438.0	431.0	38.0	10.0
No spray		408.0	432.0	21.0	15.0
LSD (P=0.050)		NS	NS	NS	NS
Var. x Planting distance					
Zm x 50 x 20 cm		532.0	370.0	37.0	8.0
Zm x 60 x 20 cm		492.0	352.0	29.0	10.0
SK x 50 x 20 cm		298.0	493.0	26.0	15.0
SK x 60 x 20 cm		313.0	559.0	30.0	12.0
LSD (P = 0.05)		NS	NS	NS	NS
Var. x Spraying regime					
Zm + 2 sprays		470.0	377.0	35.0	10.0
Zm + 3 spray		521.0	370	44.0	9.0
Zm + no spray		546.0	334.0	20.0	8.0
SK + 2 sprays		291.0	558.0	32.0	7.0
SK + 3 sprays		356.0	491.0	32.0	10.0
SK + no spray		271.0	530.0	21.0	23.0
LSD (P = 0.05)		NS	NS	NS	10.28

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Table 7: Number of pods per plant and number of pest infested seeds per plot as influenced by plant spacing and spraying regime for 2016 and 2017 cropping seasons

TREATMENT	NUMBER OF PODS PER PLANT		NUMBER OF PEST INFESTED SEEDS PER PLOT			
	Variety	YEAR	2016	2017	2016	2017
Zamzam			10.0	28.0	129.0	79.5
Soronko			7.0	36.0	66.0	90.2
LSD (P = 0.05)			2.12	6.48	51.8	NS
Planting Distance						
50 × 20cm				33.0	96.0	82.2
50 × 20cm			8.0	31.0	98.0	87.4
LSD (P = 0.05)			9.0	NS	NS	NS
			NS			
Spraying Regime						
2 sprays				39.0	103.0	59.5
3 sprays				32.0	97.0	69.1
No sprays			9.0	25.0	91.0	125.8
LSD (P = 0.05)			8.0	NS	NS	NS
			8.0			
			NS			
Var. x Planting Distance						
ZM + 50 × 20cm				28.0	131.0	84.7
ZM + 60 × 20cm				27.0	126.0	74.2
SK + 50 × 20cm			10.0	37.0	61.0	79.8
SK + 60 × 20cm			11.0	35.0	70.0	100.6
LSD (P = 0.05)			6.0	NS	NS	NS
			7.0			
			NS			
Var. x Spraying Regime						
ZM + 2 sprays				34.0	152.0	54.3
ZM + 3 sprays				29.0	106.0	77.7
ZM + no sprays				20.0	126.0	106.3
SK + 2 sprays			11.0	43.0	55.0	64.7
SK + 3 sprays			10.0	35.0	86.0	60.5
SK + no sprays			11.0	30.0	56.0	145.3
LSD (P = 0.05)			7.0	NS	NS	NS
			7.0			
			5.0			
			NS			

4.0 DISCUSSION

The high percentage plant establishment observed during 2016 and 2017 cropping seasons might be due to the initial high rainfall and temperature experienced during 2016 and 2017 cropping seasons, appropriate intra row spacing, insecticide spray application, quality and high germination ability of seeds for sowing. The significant difference between the two cowpea varieties in the shoot and fresh root weight in both 2016 and 2017 cropping seasons could be attributed to differences in variety and genetic characteristics. The increasing trend in fresh shoot weight in both cowpea varieties during 2016 and 2017 cropping seasons might be due to high rainfall couple with moderate temperature experienced during the cropping period. The significant increase in shoot fresh weight with 50 x 20 cm than 60 x 20 cm at 21 DAP during the 2016 cropping season could be due to close inter row planting distance which might have resulted in greater competition for sunlight. The non-significant difference between spraying regime, variety x spraying regime and variety x planting distance interaction in the

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shoot and fresh root weight for the entire 2016 and 2017 cropping seasons respectively might be that the treatment had no effect on planting distance and insecticide spray regime. The significant difference between 50 x 20 cm from 60 x 20 cm in fresh root weight at 35 DAP during the 2017 cropping season could be due to close inter-row planting distance. Close planting distance might have enhanced aggressive root growth through competition for soil nutrient and moisture thereby increasing the fresh root weight. Quantifying the morphology of the root system is important to determine the availability and accessibility of water and nutrients and hence improving crops for higher crop yield (Gregory, 2009).

The non-significant difference between Soronko and Zamzam in dry shoot weight from 21 to 63 days after planting (DAP) during the 2016 cropping season might be that the treatment had no effect on the two cowpea varieties. The significant difference between Zamzam and Soronko in shoot dry weight at 49 DAP and then 21 and 63 DAP during the 2016 and 2017 cropping seasons respectively could be due to differences in variety. The non-significant difference between 50 x 20 cm from 60 x 20 cm planting distance and spraying regime in shoot dry weight from 21 to 63 DAP during 2016 and 2017 cropping seasons respectively might be that the treatment had no effect on planting distance and insecticide spray regime. The significant difference between 60 x 20 cm from 50 x 20 cm in dry shoot weight at 49 DAP during the 2016 cropping season might be due to the wider planting distance that resulted in less competition for sunlight, water, and soil nutrient. The non-significant difference between the three spraying regimes, variety x planting distance and variety x spraying regime interaction in shoot dry weight for the entire 2016 and 2017 cropping seasons could be attributed to the fact that the two varieties did not respond to the treatment applied.

The non-significant difference between the two cowpea varieties in root dry weight from 21 to 49 DAP during the 2016 cropping season might be that the treatment had no effect on the two cowpea varieties. The significant difference between Soronko and Zamzam in root dry weight at 63 DAP during the 2016 cropping season could be due to differences in variety and genetic characteristics. The significant difference between Zamzam and Soronko in root dry weight for the entire 2017 cropping season could be due to differences in variety. The non-significant difference between 50 x 20 cm and 60 x 20 cm planting distance in root dry weight from 21 to 63 DAP during 2016 and 2017 cropping seasons could be that the treatment had no effect on planting distance. The significant difference between 50 x 20 cm from 60 x 20 cm at 35 DAP during the 2017 cropping season might be due to close inter-row planting distance. The non-significant difference between the three spraying regimes, variety x planting distance and variety x spraying regime interaction in root dry weight for the entire 2016 and 2017 cropping seasons could be that the treatment had no effect on planting distance and insecticide spray regime. The significant difference between Soronko sprayed two times from Zamzam sprayed 2 or 3 times as well as Soronko without insecticide spray might be due to differences in variety and its response to insecticide spray application. The non-significant difference between Soronko and Zamzam, planting distance, spraying regime, variety x planting distance and variety x spraying regime interaction in a number of plants harvested during the 2016 cropping season could be that the treatment had no effect on variety, planting distance, insecticide spraying regime and their interactions. The significant difference between Zamzam and Soronko in a number of plants harvested during the 2017 cropping season might be due to differences in variety. The significant difference between Zamzam without insecticide spray from Soronko sprayed two or three times in a number of plants harvested during the 2017 cropping season could be due to differences in variety and its response to insecticide spray. The non-significant difference between Zamzam sprayed 2 and 3 times or without insecticide spray as well as Soronko without insecticide spray and then between planting distance, spraying regime and variety x planting distance interaction in number of plants harvested during the 2017 cropping season could be that the treatment had no effect on variety, planting distance, insecticide spraying regime and their interactions. The lower number of plants harvested for the two cowpea varieties grown during the 2017 cropping season and with similar treatment than those produced during the 2016 cropping season might be due to extremely high temperature coupled with low rainfall experienced during the latter growth stage of the two cowpea varieties. Cowpea production is affected by constraints such as drought,

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salt stress and extreme temperatures that may result in poor plant growth and yield (Ajetomobi and Abiodun, 2010).

The significant difference between Soronko without insecticide spray from Soronko sprayed two or three times, as well as Zamzam, sprayed 2 or 3 times and without insecticide spray during the 2017 cropping season might be due to the variety respond to insecticide spray. The higher number of unfilled pods per plot with Soronko and Zamzam grown on 50 x 20 cm and 60 x 20 cm and sprayed 2, 3 or without insecticide spray and their interactions during the 2016 cropping season than during the 2017 cropping season might be attributed to differences in climatic conditions during the growing period coupled with low shoot fresh weight produced. The relatively lower shoot fresh weight produced during the 2016 cropping season compared to those produced during the 2017 cropping season might have resulted in less accumulation of dry matter and with low rainfall transport and distribution of photosynthates to the pods might have been quite challenging during the pod filling stage.

The significant difference between the two cowpea varieties in a number of filled pods per plot during 2016 and 2017 cropping seasons might be due to differences in variety. The non-significant difference between planting distance, spraying regime, variety × planting distance and variety × spraying regime interaction in a number of filled pods per plot in both 2016 and 2017 cropping seasons could be that the treatment had no effect on planting distance and spraying regime and their interactions.

The significant difference between the two cowpea varieties in a number of pods per plant during the 2016 and 2017 cropping seasons might be due to differences in variety, growth habit, their response to growing conditions and the genetic potential of each genotype.

The non-significant difference between planting distance, spraying regime, variety × planting distance and variety × spraying regime interaction in a number of pods per plant in both 2016 and 2017 cropping seasons might be that the treatment had no effect on variety, planting distance, spraying regime and their interactions. The higher number of pods per plant produced with Soronko and Zamzam grown on 50 x 20 cm and 60 x 20 cm spacing and sprayed 2, 3 or without insecticide spray and their interactions during the 2017 cropping season than during the 2016 cropping season might be due to relatively higher shoot fresh weight produced during the 2017 cropping season which might have enabled the two varieties to accumulate more dry matter and also have greater reproductive sink capacity coupled with high rainfall experienced which might have enhanced soil moisture content and resultant uptake of water by plants.

The significant difference between Zamzam and Soronko in a number of pest infested seeds per plot during the 2016 cropping season might be due to differences in variety. The non - significant difference between the two cowpea varieties in a number of pest infested seeds per plot during the 2017 cropping season might be that the treatment had no effect on the two cowpea varieties. The non - significant difference between planting distance, spraying regime, variety × planting distance and variety × spraying regime interaction in a number of pest infested seeds per plot in both 2016 and 2017 cropping seasons might be that the crop did not respond to treatment. The higher number of pest infested seeds per plot with Zamzam grown on 50 x 20 cm and 60 x 20 cm and sprayed 2 or 3 and its interactions during the 2016 cropping season than during the 2017 cropping season might be due to differences in climatic condition during the growing period.

5.0 CONCLUSION

Farmers are encouraged to grow Zamzam using 50 x 20 cm and spray 2 times with insecticide for high vegetative growth to serve as fodder to feed livestock. For high plant establishment and to maintain maximum numbers of plants to be harvested farmers are to grow Zamzam at 50 x 20 cm spacing and spray with insecticide 3 times. For greatest number of filled pods per plot, a high number of pods per plant and to ensure that quality seeds with least number of pest infestations are obtained farmers are to grow Soronko using 50 x 20 cm or 60 x 20 cm spacing and spray 3 times with insecticide.

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